

AI-PRISM

D3.3 – AI-PRISM Human Centred Collaborative Robotic Platform (III)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement n° 101058589. This document reflects only the author's view and the EU Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Project Title	AI-Powered human-centred Robot Interactions for Smart Manufacturing
Project Acronym	AI-PRISM
Grant Agreement No	101058589
Instrument	Research & Innovation Action
Topic	HORIZON-CL4-2021-TWIN-TRANSITION-01-01
Start Date of Project	October 1, 2022
Duration of Project	36 months

Name of the deliverable	AI-PRISM Human Robot Cooperation Ambient (III)
Number of the deliverable	D3.3
Related WP number and name	WP3
Related task number and name	T3.1, T3.2, T3.3, T3.4
Deliverable dissemination level	PU
Deliverable due date	M30
Deliverable submission date	M30
Task leader/Main author	IKE
Contributing	FBK, WINGS, TAU

partners	
Reviewer(s)	NTT ES, UPV

<p>Keywords</p> <p>Software, versions, Gitlab, AI, CI/CD</p>

Revisions

Version	Submission date	Comments	Author
v0.1	14 th February 2025	Base version	IKE, UPV
V0.2	21 st February 2025	Added contribution from partners	IKE, FBK, WINGS, TAU
V0.3	05 th March 2025	Comments from first reviewer	NTTD ES
V1	14 th March 2025	Comments from second reviewer	UPV
V2	30 th March 2025	Final version including all comments	IKE
V3	31 st March 2025	Final clean version	IKE

Disclaimer

This document is provided with no warranties whatsoever, including any warranty of merchantability, non-infringement, fitness for any particular purpose, or any other warranty with respect to any information, result, proposal, specification or sample contained or referred to herein. Any liability, including liability for infringement of any proprietary rights, regarding the use of this document or any information contained herein is disclaimed. No license, express or implied, by estoppel or otherwise, to any intellectual property rights is granted by or in connection with this document. This document is subject to change without notice. Reincarnate has been financed with support from the European Commission. This document reflects only the view of the author(s) and the European Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the

Acronyms and definitions

Acronym	Meaning
WP	Work Package
T	Task
AI	Artificial intelligence
CI	Continuous Integration
CD	Continuous Development/Deployment
2D/3D/6D	Two/three/six Dimensions

Executive summary

This document, entitled “D3.3 – AI-PRISM Human Centred Collaborative Robotic Platform (III)”, contains the description of the software developed and released during the AI-Prism project, from M7 to M30.

It includes the definition of the software versions of the robotic framework, ambient digitalization, real-time communications and collaborative simulation released during these months.

This report also includes the software currently in development. This work will be included in the next and last report D3.4.

The AI-PRISM project

AI-PRISM will provide industrial users with **human-centred artificial intelligence (AI)-based solutions to create a more efficient, resilient, digital, sustainable and high-quality European manufacturing industry.**

To do so, we will develop an **integrated and scalable environment** with solutions adapted to dynamic and unpredictable manufacturing scenarios that require tasks that are difficult to automate and where speed and versatility are essential to meet users' needs. Furthermore, the solutions will be specific to semi-automated and collaborative manufacturing in flexible production processes and will not require specific robotic programming skills.

Our solutions ecosystem will have four main pillars:

1. **A human-centred collaborative robotic platform** oriented to ease hard-to-automate manufacturing tasks.
2. **A human-robot cooperative environment** powered by trustworthy AI.
3. **Social human-agent-robots teams' collaboration** — AI-based safety monitoring and robot control mechanisms to detect and avoid unsafe situations and ensure social and physical safety.
4. **An open-access network portal** to offer compliant infrastructure.

To evaluate our solutions' performance, transferability, scalability and large-scale deployment, we will perform demonstrations in real operating environments. Specifically, in **four user pilots involving key manufacturing sectors** — furniture, food/beverage, built-in appliances and electronics —, **types of robots and industrial processes that are difficult to automate, plus a generic demonstration facility.**

In addition to seeking quantitative improvements in the manufacturing sector, **AI-PRISM aims to use technological innovation to support a paradigm shift in which AI, robotics and Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) are integrated into the manufacturing domain for the improvement of flexible production processes**, becoming a viable and widespread alternative for European factories.

During the next three years, **25 partners** from **12 countries** will join forces to make AI-PRISM a reality. From educational institutions to research and technology organisations, robot manufacturers, industries and use case providers; our interdisciplinary consortium brings together all the actors of the human-robot collaboration value chain and involves key experts in SSH, standardisation, exploitation, and dissemination.

Contents

Executive summary.....	5
1. Introduction	9
1.1. Objectives and methodology.....	9
1.2. Modules guidelines	10
1.3. Status guidelines	10
2. Architecture of the Human Centred Collaborative Robotic Platform.....	11
3. Modules.....	12
3.1. Collaborative Multiagent ROS based Robotic framework (IKE).....	12
3.1.1. ROS Framework – RF (IKER).....	12
3.1.2. Base Hardware – BH (IKER).....	13
3.1.2.1 Universal Robots Driver	13
3.1.2.2 Sawyer Robot Driver	14
3.1.2.3 Dobot CR10 Robot Driver	14
3.1.2.4 Dobot CR5 Robot Driver	15
3.1.2.5 Ridgeback Robot Driver	16
3.1.2.6 Comau Racer 5 Robot Driver	16
3.1.2.7 KUKA iiwa Driver	17
3.1.2.8 Oculus Touch Driver	18
3.1.2.9 Thorlabs Precision Table Driver	19
3.1.2.10 Siemens PLC Driver.....	20
3.1.2.11 SPS Electronic Safety Tester KT1885 Driver	20
3.1.2.12 Schmalz SCG-HSS 1xE100 AR 25 47 Gripper Driver	21
3.1.2.13 Stationary Camera System Driver	22
3.2. Ambient digitalization for Human-Robot Collaboration (FBK).....	22
3.2.1. Ambient sensing infrastructure – AS (FBK).....	22
3.2.1.1 a2A5320-23ucBAS Basler ace Driver	23
3.2.1.2 Microphone 130F21 ICP® ARRAY Driver	23

3.2.1.3	Delta Optical Driver	24
3.2.1.4	ESP32-SI7021 humidity and temperature sensor Driver	25
3.2.1.5	Intel RealSense RGB-D Camera Driver	25
3.2.1.6	SEN54-SDN Wireless Environmental Sensor Driver	26
3.2.1.7	Openmote-B Wireless Environmental Sensor Driver	27
3.2.1.8	HOYUKO UTM-30LX-EW 2D LIDAR Driver	27
3.2.1.9	UWB Driver	28
3.2.1.10	ZED Camera Driver	29
3.2.2.	Ambient Digitalization Modules – AD (FBK)	29
3.3.	Real-Time communications for sensor and platform integration and control (WINGS)	31
3.3.1.	Communications Modules – CM (IKER)	31
3.3.2.	Real Time Communications Network (HMI) Modules – HI (ITI)	32
3.3.3.	IIoT Platform – IP (WINGS)	33
3.3.4.	Data Platform – DS (WINGS)	34
3.4.	Collaborative Simulation Platform (TAU)	35
3.4.1.	Simulation Environment – SE (TAU)	35
4.	Conclusions	37
4.1.1.	Summary	37
4.1.2.	Next steps	37

1. Introduction

1.1. Objectives and methodology

This deliverable describes the consecutive releases of the AI-PRISM software which includes libraries for real time communication, ambient digitalization, and simulation. This includes code repositories and pipelines to support the development of new modules, their deployment and testing. The simulation platform supports specific developed modules for agent simulation and for collaboration and risks evaluation.

The following specific objectives are targeted in WP3:

- Design and validation of a robotic framework based on ROS for the integration of the technological modules.
- A digitalization module able to map the environment from pre-existing data-models and different sensors in the environment.
- A unified AI-PRISM Data Model that described data flows and offers access to topics and data management functions.
- A new simulation platform that will enable the development of a virtual environment of specific production plants or lines, including the interaction between existing agents.

The ecosystem of solutions encompasses many different components, including new components to include new features, applications, or scenarios. For this reason, it is important to note that the list of components hereby presented corresponds to the status at the reporting month M30. The documentation of the latest version of AI-PRISM components is maintained online in <https://documentation.aiprism-srv.cigip.upv.es/guides/>.

1.2. Modules guidelines

The description of the modules present in this deliverable will follow the next structure:

Module name		Name of the current module		
General description		Description of the module, its reach and the necessary interactions with others.		
Gitlab link		Link to the repository (if it applies to the module)		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	Expected date of the version	General description of the version	Milestones achieved in this version	Status of the version (described in Section 1.3)
...		(Repeat for subsequent versions)		

1.3. Status guidelines

Status	Description
Planned	Task defined and assigned to an Epic
In progress	Task under current development
Ready to test	Task developed and ready to be tested
Completed	Task finished and tested
On hold	Task temporary paused

2. Architecture of the Human Centred Collaborative Robotic Platform

The Human Centred Collaborative Robotic Platform is divided into four modules that are interconnected among them to provide the requested result.

Its deployment is divided into two main parts: the one located in the production plant, and the one in the cloud.

In the production plant, the ROS framework, along with the necessary drivers for the data acquisition from the sensors and the ones for the control of the actuators, are deployed. The algorithms that will process the data obtained from the sensors and digitalize the work environment will be in this side as well.

All this information recollected and processed in the plant will be sent, through communication in real time, to the data platform that is in remote servers. This platform provides long-term storage services, useful to build comprehensive datasets, a data management API and tools to build rich data visualizations. Additionally, AI-PRISM provides a cluster management service that allows to deploy HRC components anywhere from the cloud to the far-edge. This provides flexibility to adapt to different use case scenarios and requirements. Components like AI enhancing perception modules processing sensor data or AI enhancing reasoning modules responding to perceived events with commands for hardware can be located in different nodes to balance AI workloads or provide the require performance. Additional features (as programming by demonstration, human-machine interaction, and perception enhancement, among others) will be also applied, either from the cloud or local, when it suits the application. This document specifically addresses the components that have been developed within WP3, which are described in this document, are available in the following repository:

<https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp3>

[Complementary, deliverable D4.3 describes the components that have been developed in WP4.](#)

3. Modules

3.1. Collaborative Multiagent ROS based Robotic framework (IKE)

Task 3.1 is focused on developing the framework for the deployment of collaborative robotic applications based on ROS2, providing the requested software, dependencies and drivers of the required hardware.

The Gitlab software repository is available here:

<https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp3/ros-framework>

3.1.1. ROS Framework – RF (IKER)

Module name		ROS Framework		
General description		The ROS Framework acts as a nexus between all the different devices and modules required to command a robot, ranging from the controller that gathers data to the one that conducts the robot, including any module involved in the tasks in between (data treatment, path planning and AI algorithms, among others).		
Gitlab link		https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp3/ros-framework/ros2_base		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	-	First functional Gitlab instance. It includes the code repository and basic project templates.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First Gitlab instance • First templates 	Completed
2.0	December 31 st , 2023	Docker-compose for the image deployment. Network for the connection of modules to the image.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A lightweight image based on Ubuntu 22.04 is available for x86 devices. • Added deployment documentation. 	Completed
3.0	March 20 st , 2025	Docker-compose image for the deployment of non-development image.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A base image with ROS2 that provides GPU capabilities is available for x86 devices. 	Completed

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A base image with ROS2 that provides GPU capabilities is available for arm64 devices (for Jetson units). • Added deployment documentation. 	
4.0	TBD	Dynamic docker image creator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dynamic docker image generation for the deployment in Kubernetes. 	In progress

3.1.2. Base Hardware – BH (IKER)

3.1.2.1 Universal Robots Driver

Module name	Universal Robots Driver			
General description	<p>Module for the deployment of ROS2 drivers for the control of an UR10e 6D collaborative robotic arm.</p>			
Gitlab link	https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp3/ros-framework/base_hardware/universal_robots			
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	-	First functional Gitlab instance. It includes code repository and basic project templates.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First Gitlab instance • First templates 	Completed
2.0	February 21 st , 2025	Uploaded into the repository the ROS2 module for the control of the hardware of the UR10e robotic arm	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ROS2 drivers for the UR10e robot available in repository. 	Completed

3.1.2.2 Sawyer Robot Driver

Module name		Sawyer Robot Driver		
General description		<p>Module for the deployment of ROS2 drivers for the control of a Sawyer robotic arm.</p>		
Gitlab link		https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp3/ros-framework/base_hardware/sawyer_robot		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	-	First functional Gitlab instance. It includes code repository and basic project templates.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First Gitlab instance • First templates 	Completed
2.0	December 31 st , 2023	Sawyer robot image added by combining ROS1 and ROS2 images and ROS-bridge.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ROS2 support for Sawyer robot. • Docker-compose file for deployment 	Completed

3.1.2.3 Dobot CR10 Robot Driver

Module name		Dobot CR10 Robot Driver		
General description		Module for the deployment of ROS2 drivers to control the Dobot CR10 robotic arm.		

Gitlab link		https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp3/ros-framework/base_hardware/dobot_cr		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	-	First functional Gitlab instance. It includes a code repository and basic project templates.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First Gitlab instance • First templates 	Completed
1.1	April 15 th , 2024	Dockerfile and Docker-compose files added.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ROS2 support. • Container deployment. 	Completed

3.1.2.4 Dobot CR5 Robot Driver

Module name	Dobot CR5 Robot Driver
General description	<p>Module for the deployment of ROS2 drivers for the control the Dobot CR5 robotic arm</p> <div style="text-align: center;"> </div>
Gitlab link	https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp3/ros-framework/base_hardware/dobot_cr

Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	-	First functional Gitlab instance. It includes a code repository and basic project templates.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First Gitlab instance • First templates 	Completed
1.1	April 15 th , 2024	Dockerfile and Docker-compose files added.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ROS2 support. • Container deployment. 	Completed

3.1.2.5 Ridgeback Robot Driver

Module name	Ridgeback Robot Driver			
General description	<p>Module for the deployment of ROS2 drivers for the control the Clearpath Ridgeback omnidirectional mobile manipulation robot.</p>			
Gitlab link	https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp3/ros-framework/base_hardware/clearpath_ridgeback			
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	-	First functional Gitlab instance. It includes code repository and basic project templates.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First Gitlab instance • First templates 	Completed
2.0	April 15 th , 2024	Ridgeback AMR image added by combining ROS1 and ROS2 images and ROS-bridge.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ROS2 support for Ridgeback AMR. • Container deployment. 	Completed

3.1.2.6 Comau Racer 5 Robot Driver

Module name	Comau Racer 5 Robot Driver
-------------	----------------------------

General description		Module for the deployment of the ROS2 drivers for the Comau Racer 5 robotic arm. 		
Gitlab link		https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp3/ros-framework/base_hardware/comau_racer_5		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	-	First functional Gitlab instance. It includes code repository and basic project templates.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First Gitlab instance • First templates 	Completed
2.0	February 21 st , 2025	Uploaded into the repository the ROS2 module for the control of the hardware of the Comau Racer 5 robotic arm	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ROS2 drivers for the Comau Racer 5 robot available in repository. 	Completed

3.1.2.7 KUKA iiwa Driver

Module name	KUKA iiwa Driver
General description	Module for the deployment of the ROS2-based control for the KUKA iiwa robotic arm (through shared memory).

Gitlab link		https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp3/ros-framework/base_hardware/kuka_iiwa		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	-	First functional Gitlab instance. It includes code repository and basic project templates.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First Gitlab instance • First templates 	Completed
2.0	May 2025	Development of ROS2-based control of the robotic arm through shared memory.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ROS2-based interface drivers for the control of the arm. 	In progress

3.1.2.8 Oculus Touch Driver

Module name	Oculus Touch Driver
General description	<p>Module that contains the necessary information for the deployment of the Oculus Touch device in Ubuntu systems.</p> <div style="text-align: center;"> </div>
Gitlab link	https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp3/ros-framework/base_hardware/oculus-touch-driver
Released versions	

Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	-	First functional Gitlab instance. It includes code repository and basic project templates.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First Gitlab instance • First templates 	Completed
2.0	December 31 st , 2023	Documentation regarding the Oculus Touch support for Ubuntu systems added.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Oculus Touch documentation added to the repository. 	Completed

3.1.2.9 Thorlabs Precision Table Driver

Module name	Thorlabs Precision Table Driver			
General description	Module that contains the ROS2 drivers for the control of the Thorlabs KMTS50E_M Precision table.			
Gitlab link	https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp3/ros-framework/base_hardware/thorlabs_kmts50e_m			
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	-	First functional Gitlab instance. It includes code repository and basic project templates.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First Gitlab instance • First templates 	Completed
2.0	February 21 st , 2025	Uploaded into the repository the ROS2 module for the control of the hardware of the Thorlabs Precision Table	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ROS2 drivers for the Thorlabs Precision Table KMTS50E available in repository. 	Completed

3.1.2.10 Siemens PLC Driver

Module name		Thorlabs Precision Table Driver		
General description		Module that contains the ROS2 drivers for interfacing with Siemens PLCs. 		
Gitlab link		https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp3/ros-framework/base_hardware/siemens_plc		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	-	First functional Gitlab instance. It includes code repository and basic project templates.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First Gitlab instance • First templates 	Completed
2.0	March 28 th , 2025	Uploaded into the repository the ROS2 module for interfacing with Siemens PLCs using the Snap7 protocol	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ROS2 drivers for the Siemens PLCs available in repository. 	Completed

3.1.2.11 SPS Electronic Safety Tester KT1885 Driver

Module name		SPS Electronic Safety Tester KT1885 Driver		
General description		Module that contains the necessary ROS2 drivers for the deployment of the KT1885 safety tester. 		
Gitlab link		https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp3/ros-framework/base_hardware/sps-electronic-safety-tester-kt1885		
Released versions				

Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	-	First functional Gitlab instance. It includes code repository and basic project templates.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> First Gitlab instance First templates 	Completed
2.0	February 21 st , 2025	Uploaded into the repository the ROS2 module for the control of the hardware of the Safety Tester KT1885.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ROS2 drivers for the SPS Electronic Safety Tester KT1885 available in repository. 	Completed

3.1.2.12 Schmalz SCG-HSS 1xE100 AR 25 47 Gripper Driver

Module name		Schmalz SCG-HSS 1xE100 AR 25 47 Gripper Driver		
General description		<p>Module that contains the necessary ROS2 drivers for the deployment of the Schmalz SCG-HSS 1xE100 AR 25 47 Gripper.</p>		
Gitlab link		https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp3/ros-framework/base_hardware/scg-hss-1xe100-ar-25-47		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	-	First functional Gitlab instance. It includes code repository and basic project templates.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> First Gitlab instance First templates 	Completed
2.0	May 2025	Adaptation of the drivers to ROS2 Development of ROS2 drivers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ROS2 drivers for the SCG-HSS 1xE100 AR 25 47 	In progress

3.1.2.13 Stationary Camera System Driver

Module name		Stationary Camera System Driver		
General description		Module that contains the necessary ROS2 drivers for the deployment of the Wenglor industrial camera and Planistar Illumination panel drivers.		
Gitlab link		https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp3/ros-framework/base_hardware/stationary_camera_system		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	-	First functional Gitlab instance. It includes code repository and basic project templates.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First Gitlab instance • First templates 	Completed
2.0	May 2025	Development of ROS2 drivers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ROS2 drivers for the Wenglor industrial camera and Planistar Illumination panel. 	In progress

3.2. Ambient digitalization for Human-Robot Collaboration (FBK)

Task 3.2 gathers the necessary drivers for the monitoring of the environment of the robotic deployment and its digitalization by sensor data fusion. Information from pre-existing data models and the one obtained from the sensors will be used for the generation of point-cloud data structures that will describe the surroundings of the robot.

The Gitlab software repository is available here:

<https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp3/ambient-digitalization>

3.2.1. Ambient sensing infrastructure – AS (FBK)

Interfaces to control sensing infrastructure equipment. Communication modules will manage and exchange information with sensing hardware devices using these drivers.

3.2.1.1 a2A5320-23ucBAS Basler ace Driver

Module name		a2A5320-23ucBAS Basler ace Driver		
General description		Module that contains the necessary ROS2 drivers for the deployment of the a2A5320-23ucBAS barcode scanner. 		
Gitlab link		https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp3/ros-framework/base_hardware/a2a5320-23ucbas		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	-	First functional Gitlab instance. It includes code repository and basic project templates.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First Gitlab instance • First templates 	Completed
2.0	February 21 st , 2025	Uploaded into the repository the ROS2 module for the data acquisition of the a2A5320-23ucBAS barcode scanner.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ROS2 drivers for the a2A5320-23ucBAS barcode scanner available in repository. 	Completed

3.2.1.2 Microphone 130F21 ICP® ARRAY Driver

Module name		Microphone 130F21 ICP® ARRAY Driver		
General description		Module that contains the necessary ROS2 drivers for the deployment of the 130F21 ICP Microphone. 		
Gitlab link		https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp3/ros-framework/base_hardware/130f21		
Released versions				

Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	-	First functional Gitlab instance. It includes code repository and basic project templates.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First Gitlab instance • First templates 	Completed
2.0	February 21 st , 2025	Uploaded into the repository the ROS2 module for the data acquisition of the 130F21 ICP Microphone.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ROS2 drivers for the 130F21 ICP Microphone available in repository. 	Completed

3.2.1.3 Delta Optical Driver

Module name		Delta optical Driver		
General description		<p>Module that contains the necessary ROS2 drivers for the deployment of the Delta Optical DLT camera.</p>		
Gitlab link		https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp3/ros-framework/base_hardware/dlt_cam		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	-	First functional Gitlab instance. It includes code repository and basic project templates.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First Gitlab instance • First templates 	Completed
2.0	February 21 st , 2025	Uploaded into the repository the ROS2 module for the data acquisition of the Delta Optical DLT camera.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ROS2 drivers for the Delta Optical DLT camera available in repository. 	Completed

3.2.1.4 ESP32-SI7021 humidity and temperature sensor Driver

Module name		ESP32-SI7021 humidity and temperature sensor Driver		
General description		Module that contains the necessary ROS2 drivers for the deployment of the SI7021 humidity and temperature sensor by a ESP32 microcontroller.		
Gitlab link		https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp3/ros-framework/base_hardware/micro-ros-esp32-sensors		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	-	First functional Gitlab instance. It includes code repository and basic project templates.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First Gitlab instance • First templates 	Completed
2.0	February 21 st , 2025	Uploaded into the repository the ROS2 module for the data acquisition of the SI7021 sensor through a ESP32 microcontroller.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ROS2 drivers for the reading of humidity and temperature sensors available in repository. 	Completed

3.2.1.5 Intel RealSense RGB-D Camera Driver

Module name		Intel RealSense RGB-D Camera Driver		
General description		<p>Module that contains the necessary ROS2 drivers for the deployment of the RealSense RGB-D cameras.</p>		
Gitlab link		https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp3/ambient-digitalization/ambient-digitalization-modules-ad-fbk/realsense		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status

1.0	-	First functional Gitlab instance. It includes code repository and basic project templates.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First Gitlab instance • First templates 	Completed
2.0	December 31 st 2023	Uploaded into the repository the ROS2 module for the data acquisition of the RealSense D435 cameras.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ROS2 drivers for the RealSense D435 cameras available in repository. 	Completed
3.0	September 9 th , 2024	Implemented support for the deprecated RealSense L515 cameras.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ROS2 drivers for the deprecated RealSense L515 cameras available in repository. 	Completed

3.2.1.6 SEN54-SDN Wireless Environmental Sensor Driver

Module name	SEN54-SDN Wireless Environmental Sensor Driver			
General description	<p>Module that contains the necessary ROS2 drivers for the deployment of the SEN54-SDN wireless environmental driver.</p>			
Gitlab link	https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp3/ros-framework/base_hardware/sen54-sdn			
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	-	First functional Gitlab instance. It includes code repository and basic project templates.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First Gitlab instance • First templates 	Completed
2.0	February 21 st , 2025	First version of the drivers for the SEN54-SDN wireless environmental sensor.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Drivers of the SEN54-SDN wireless environmental sensor uploaded into the repository. 	Completed
3.0	May 2025	Adaptation of the drivers to ROS2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ROS2 drivers for the SEN54-SDN wireless environmental sensor 	In progress

3.2.1.7 Openmote-B Wireless Environmental Sensor Driver

Module name		Openmote-B Wireless Environmental Sensor Driver		
General description		Module that contains the necessary ROS2 drivers for the deployment of the Openmote-B wireless environmental driver.		
Gitlab link		https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp3/ros-framework/base_hardware/openmote-b		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	-	First functional Gitlab instance. It includes code repository and basic project templates.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First Gitlab instance • First templates 	Completed
2.0	February 21 st , 2025	First version of the drivers for the Openmote-B wireless environmental sensor.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Drivers of the Openmote-B wireless environmental sensor uploaded into the repository. 	Completed
3.0	May 2025	Adaptation of the drivers to ROS2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ROS2 drivers for the Openmote-B wireless environmental sensor 	In progress

3.2.1.8 HOYUKO UTM-30LX-EW 2D LIDAR Driver

Module name		HOYUKO UTM-30LX-EW 2D LIDAR Driver		
General description		<p>Module that contains the necessary ROS2 drivers for the deployment of the Hoyuko UTM-30LX-EW 2D Lidar.</p>		
Gitlab link		https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp3/ros-framework/base_hardware/hokuyo_utm_30lx_ew		

Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	-	First functional Gitlab instance. It includes code repository and basic project templates.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First Gitlab instance • First templates 	Completed
1.1	April 15 th , 2024	Dockerfile and Docker-compose files added.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ROS2 support. • Container deployment. 	Completed

3.2.1.9 UWB Driver

Module name		UWB Driver		
General description		This module provides a ROS2 node that reads data from the Ultra-Wide Band server and sends it to AMR to follow the UWB tag.		
Gitlab link		https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp3/ros-framework/base_hardware/uwb		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	-	First functional Gitlab instance. It includes code repository and basic project templates.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First Gitlab instance • First templates 	Completed
2.0	March 31 st , 2025	ROS2 node used to receive data from the UWB server and a launch file implementing this node with Nav2 to follow the target tag. It creates a UDP socket and publishes the filtered information received from the server.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ROS2 driver for the UWB- AMR follow-me application available in repository. 	Completed

3.2.1.10 ZED Camera Driver

Module name		ZED Camera Driver		
General description		<p>Module that contains the necessary ROS2 drivers for the deployment of the ZED 2I camera.</p>		
Gitlab link		https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp3/ros-framework/base_hardware/ZED_2I		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	-	First functional Gitlab instance. It includes code repository and basic project templates.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First Gitlab instance • First templates 	Completed
2.0	February 21 st , 2025	Uploaded into the repository the ROS2 module for the data acquisition of the ZED 2I camera.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ROS2 drivers for the ZED 2I camera available in repository. 	Completed

3.2.2. Ambient Digitalization Modules – AD (FBK)

Module name		Ambient Digitalization Modules		
General description		Interfaces to integrate ambient digitalization modules into the ROS framework.		
Gitlab link				
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	-	This is the first functional Gitlab	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First Gitlab instance • First templates 	Completed

		instance. It includes code repository and basic project templates.		
2.0	TBD	ROS implementations of the digitalization tools for each of the use case pilots.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • VIGO digitalization • SIL hood digitalization • AW chairs digitalization 	In progress
3.0	September 9 th , 2024	Dockerized version of the FBK chair detection demo	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deployment through Docker of the pose estimator algorithm. 	Completed
4.0	February 21 st , 2025	Upgrade of the 3D encoder, 400 times faster than the previous one. Developed methods for extrinsic calibration of RGBD sensors (chessboard-based and deep learning-based)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New version of the 3D encoder. • 2 methods for extrinsic calibration 	Completed

3.3. Real-Time communications for sensor and platform integration and control (WINGS)

Task 3.3 develops the communication between the sensors deployed for the robotic application and the data platform and services. A unified data model is declared for describing data flows among processes and services. Data management for treatment and device management for control and reconfiguration will be performed, as well as the deployment of real-time communications (both wired and wireless). The data platform will offer an API to enable access to topics and data records.

The Gitlab software repository is available here:

<https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp3/t3.3-real-time-communications>

3.3.1. Communications Modules – CM (IKER)

Module name		Communications Modules		
General description		Device Management interfaces to manage robots and ambient sensing infrastructure devices in the ambient from AI-PRISM. The IIoT Platform will use these interfaces to manage devices and communications with higher layers in a centralized way.		
Gitlab link		https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp3/t3.3-real-time-communications/communications_modules		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	-	This is the first functional Gitlab instance. It includes code repository and basic project templates.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First Gitlab instance • First templates 	Completed
2.0	March 31 st 2024	This module captures any message streamed through a ROS2 topic starting with /mqtt/ and streams it through an MQTT topic to the IIoT platform.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MQTT bridge image added 	Completed

3.0	TBD	Add dynamic support for other kinds of messages.	Dynamic support for non-predefined messages.	In progress
------------	-----	--	--	-------------

3.3.2. Real Time Communications Network (HMI) Modules – HI (ITI)

Module name		Real Time Communications Network (HMI) Modules		
General description		Interfaces to manage and control communications network equipment. The IIoT Platform will use these (northbound) interfaces of real time communications infrastructure to manage QoS in the network.		
Gitlab link		https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp3/t3.3-real-time-communications/real-time-communications-network-modules		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	-	This is the first functional Gitlab instance. It includes code repository and basic project templates.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First Gitlab instance • First templates 	Completed
2.0	March 31 st 2024	This module connects a software-defined wireless sensor network and an orchestration system. The wireless sensor network gathers data and upshares it through a set of MQTT brokers.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SD-IWSN Southbound • MQTT Bridge 	Completed
3.0	September 9 th 2024	First release of the SDN controller, integrated with orchestration capabilities for wireless devices.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SDN Controller • Resource allocation • Northbound API 	Completed
4.0	February 18 st , 2025	Second release of the SDN controller, with low layer device configuration and management. Sending real data from pilots.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SDN Controller • Southbound API 	Completed

5.0	TBD	This release adds orchestration capabilities to wireless devices, enabling seamless API integration and interoperability with external components.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Remote Orchestration • SDN Controller • SD-IWSN 	In progress
-----	-----	--	---	-------------

3.3.3. IIoT Platform – IP (WINGS)

Module name		IIoT Platform		
General description		Interfaces to equipment from higher-level reasoning modules. Higher-level reasoning modules use these interfaces to define or update scheduled tasks, control rules or constraints.		
Gitlab link		Proprietary – Access granted upon agreement		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	March 30th, 2023	First release and deployment. Connectivity check with sensors and reliable data transfer.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First instance • IIoT sensors provisioning • Secure MQTT brokers 	Completed
2.0	November 10th, 2023	Second release and deployment. Video sources are now supported.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Video stream integration 	Completed
2.1	January 25th, 2024	Major update to include graphical elements such as floorplans of warehouses and other widgets.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Updates on Floorplan and Video widgets 	Completed

3.3.4. Data Platform – DS (WINGS)

Module name		Data Platform		
General description		The Data Platform provides centralized batch and streaming services to access data through these interfaces.		
Gitlab link		Proprietary – Access granted upon agreement		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	March 30th, 2023	First release and deployment.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First instance 	Completed
2.0	October 17th, 2023	Incoming data are saved related to time and only if the value changes, to optimize storage.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Optimized time series storage with retention & compression policies 	Completed
3.0	January 25th, 2024	Data representation for both time series and pie charts require batching.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support for visualization of historical data in tables and charts 	Completed

3.4. Collaborative Simulation Platform (TAU)

Task 3.4 is focused on the development of a simulation platform that will combine elements and environments from already existing simulation software with robotic and human agents, allowing the design and simulation of production plants or lines. This will allow the study of robotic collaboration and risk analysis.

The Gitlab software repository is available here:

<https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp3/t3.4-collaborative-simulation-platform>

3.4.1. Simulation Environment – SE (TAU)

Module name		Simulation Environment		
General description		Tool that allows photorealistic 3D representations of a collaborative manufacture environment, including robots, industrial equipment, and human agents. It will help industrial partners to simulate processes in a more realistic way, considering human operators in the simulation. With the SE, users will be able to recreate production plants and lines, taking into consideration interactions between the existing agents in the environment and integrating human avatars.		
Gitlab link		https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp3/t3.4-collaborative-simulation-platform/simulation-environment_se_tau		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	-	This is the first functional Gitlab instance. It includes code repository and basic project templates.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First Gitlab instance • First templates 	Completed
2.0	31 st March 2024	First release of the database structure (SQLite) of the Simulation Environment and the front-end of the HRPI (Human-Robot Physical Interaction) module based on Nvidia Omniverse.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Database creation • Front-end of the HRPI module based provided mock-ups 	Completed
3.0	9 th September 2024	First release of the back-end of the HRPI module.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First release of photo-realistic digital human 	Completed

		First integration of photo-realistic digital human workers.	workers in the scene with their animations. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Functionality that allows the scene configuration. 	
4.0	TBD	Second release of the back-end of the HRPI module with its functionalities.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Back-end of HRPI module 	In progress

4. Conclusions

4.1.1. Summary

This document describes the versions of the software components of the AI-PRISM human-centered collaborative robotic platform for smart manufacturing that have been developed from months 7 to 30. The document outlines modules encompassing a ROS-based robotic framework, ambient digitalization tools using different sensors, real-time communication systems, and a collaborative simulation platform. Each module's description includes its purpose in the project, links to software, and the status and features of its released versions. The guidelines to develop documentation are also described in sections 1.2 and 1.3 for a homogeneous description.

4.1.2. Next steps

During the next 6 months, the software that is currently in progress, indicated in this document, will be developed and included in the next and final deliverable.